

1 The costs of paraphyletic classification in the world's most endangered fishes

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9
10 **Abstract**

11 Taxonomy is the organizing principle underlying how scientists, policymakers, and the public
12 engage with biological diversity. Yet, the ongoing transition from Linnaean ranks to explicitly
13 phylogenetic, rank-free taxonomy remains controversial. The tension between phylogenetic
14 accuracy and nomenclatural stability is nowhere more consequential than in clades facing
15 imminent extinction. In these cases, taxonomy directly shapes legal protections, conservation
16 prioritization, and the identification of evolutionarily significant units. This means that
17 taxonomic revisions carry consequences for the survival of lineages that extend well beyond their
18 position in the catalog of biodiversity. Here, we argue that taxonomic revision using
19 phylogenetic rank-free nomenclature provides a much-needed quantitative basis for conservation
20 biology. We focus on the case of sturgeons (*Acipenseridae*), a clade of Holarctic ray-finned
21 fishes in which all species are at risk of extinction. Recently, the IUCN Sturgeon Specialist
22 Group (SSG) voted unanimously to reject a phylogenetic rank-free taxonomy of this clade
23 published in 2025. A conservative alternative classification proposed by the SSG sustains a

24 paraphyletic concept of *Acipenser* that fails on the group's stated terms of conserving names that
25 reflect morphology and other aspects of natural history. We argue that the SSG rejection
26 exemplifies a recurring response in which the practical costs of taxonomic change are invoked to
27 resist classifications that are demonstrably more reflective of evolutionary history. This has
28 direct consequences for conservation through the misrepresentation of evolutionary diversity, the
29 distortion of conservation prioritization metrics, and the misidentification of evolutionarily
30 significant units. Taxonomies based on empirically reconstructed evolutionary relationships do
31 not inhibit conservation but inform the protection of Earth's biological heritage.

33 **Introduction**

34 Every decision in conservation biology, from species listings to the delineation of
35 protected areas, depends on a prior decision about what counts as a distinct biological entity.
36 When taxonomies accurately reflect evolutionary relationships, they convey information about
37 common ancestry and the distribution of biological diversity that is directly useful for research
38 and management; when they do not, taxonomies can misdirect basic research and result in the
39 misallocation of conservation resources (Garnett and Christidis 2017; Padial et al. 2010). The
40 stakes of getting classification right are therefore highest in lineages where conservation
41 decisions are most urgent.

42 The transition from ranked classification toward explicitly phylogenetic, rank-free
43 taxonomy is arguably the most important transformation in biological nomenclature since
44 Linnaeus proposed a ranked system of classifying biodiversity (Cantino and de Queiroz 2020; de
45 Queiroz and Gauthier 1994; Laurin 2023). This transition is driven by a persistent set of
46 problems with the traditional Linnean system. Linnaean ranked categories are not biologically

47 comparable across taxa, ranked classification produces redundant and uninformative group
48 names, and the rank-based system creates nomenclatural conflicts rather than resolving them
49 whenever phylogenetic hypotheses improve (de Queiroz and Gauthier 1990; de Queiroz and
50 Gauthier 1994; Laurin 2024). Recent work has begun to implement this framework across ray-
51 finned fishes, applying PhyloCode-inspired phylogenetic definitions to actinopterygian clade
52 names and revising the taxonomy of species-rich groups such as wrasses and parrotfishes
53 (*Labridae*) to reflect consistent phylogenetic resolution of traditionally recognized but para- and
54 polyphyletic taxa (Near et al. 2025; Near and Thacker 2024). In both cases, the argument is not
55 only that taxa happen to be para- or polyphyletic when species are analyzed using phylogenetic
56 methods, but also that the Linnaean ranked system is structurally incapable of stably representing
57 natural groups as phylogenetic hypotheses improve (de Queiroz and Gauthier 1992; de Queiroz
58 and Gauthier 1994).

59 Sturgeons comprise the clade *Acipenseridae*, a lineage of 27 living species distributed
60 across the Northern Hemisphere in marine coastal waters, large rivers, and lakes from the
61 Atlantic and Pacific coasts of North America to Europe, the Black and Caspian seas, Siberian
62 rivers, and the river systems of East Asia (Bemis et al. 1997; Bemis and Kynard 1997;
63 Choudhury and Dick 1998). Sturgeons and their sister group, the paddlefishes (*Polyodontidae*),
64 are classified in *Acipenseriformes* and are characterized as living fossils based on their
65 morphological conservatism, with body plans of living species closely resembling those of
66 extinct forms from the Late Cretaceous, and their dramatically reduced molecular evolutionary
67 rates relative to other ray-finned fishes (Brownstein et al. 2024; Krieger and Fuerst 2002).
68 *Acipenseriformes* originated in the Jurassic, with crown *Acipenseridae* diverging approximately
69 100 million years ago, meaning that the genera of living sturgeons represent lineages with deep

70 and independent evolutionary histories that diverged from one another in the Cretaceous and
71 early Paleogene (Brownstein and Near 2025). Sturgeons have long been economically important,
72 particularly for the international trade in black caviar, but the 20th century saw a rapid expansion
73 of this trade that drove severe population declines across the family, a trajectory now
74 compounded by the growth of captive aquaculture (Rueness et al. 2025).

75 All 27 living species of sturgeons are threatened with extinction: 17 are currently
76 assessed as Critically Endangered, three are Endangered, four are Vulnerable, and one is Extinct
77 in the Wild (IUCN 2026). Sturgeons are protected by a dense network of conservation measures,
78 from CITES (Rueness et al. 2025) and IUCN Red List assessments (IUCN 2026) to the EU
79 Habitats Directive (Strat and Gheorghe 2023), HELCOM, the Bern Convention (Congiu et al.
80 2023; Gessner et al. 2019), and the U.S. Endangered Species Act. Because these instruments are
81 tied to specific genus and species names, taxonomy changes carry policy consequences.
82 Researchers have recognized for decades that the traditional classification of *Acipenseridae*
83 conflicts with its phylogeny (Figure 1) (Brownstein and Near 2025). Both *Acipenser* and *Huso*,
84 which together include 21 of the 27 species of sturgeons, are resolved as paraphyletic in every
85 molecular and morphological analysis published since the late 1990s (Birstein and DeSalle 1998;
86 Birstein et al. 2002; Dadkhah et al. 2023; Dillman et al. 2007; Hilton et al. 2011; Krieger et al.
87 2008; Luo et al. 2019; Peng et al. 2007; Shedko 2022; Shen et al. 2020). This makes sturgeons an
88 unusually high-stakes test case for how the scientific community navigates the conflict between
89 taxonomic stability and phylogenetic accuracy (Brownstein and Near 2026; Kottelat and Freyhof
90 2025).

91 In 2025, we applied the principles of *PhyloCode* and a well-resolved phylogeny to revise
92 the taxonomy of sturgeons (*Acipenseridae*) using a rank-free, phylogeny-based framework

93 (Brownstein and Near 2025). Our rank-free taxonomy of *Acipenseridae* drew on analyses of
94 mitochondrial DNA (cytochrome *b*), 30 single-copy nuclear orthologs, discretely coded
95 morphological characters, and combined molecular and morphological datasets (Brownstein and
96 Near 2025). The new rank-free taxonomy identified five monophyletic groups treated as genera
97 under the ICZN: *Acipenser* sensu stricto (comprising *A. sturio*, *A. oxyrinchus*, and *A. desotoi*),
98 the resurrected genus *Sinosturio* (seven species mostly distributed in and around the Pacific
99 Ocean), an expanded *Huso* (eleven species distributed in the Atlantic and Eurasia), and the
100 unaltered delimitations of *Scaphirhynchus* and *Pseudoscaphirhynchus* (Figure 1). In this
101 taxonomy, all acipenserid genera are monophyletic (Brownstein and Near 2025), resolving the
102 paraphyly of *Acipenser* and *Huso* that has characterized the taxonomy of *Acipenseridae* for
103 decades (Birstein and DeSalle 1998; Brownstein and Near 2025; Hilton et al. 2011; Kottelat and
104 Freyhof 2025; Luo et al. 2019).

105 In October 2025, during the 10th International Sturgeon Symposium in Yichang, China,
106 the IUCN SSG convened a workshop that voted unanimously to reject the revised taxonomy of
107 sturgeons presented in Brownstein and Near (2025) (North American Sturgeon & Paddlefish
108 Society 2025, <https://nasps-sturgeon.org/acipenseridae-taxonomy/>). The SSG statement cited
109 weak statistical support for the phylogenies that provide the basis of the taxonomy, missing data
110 in DNA sequence alignments, incompatibility with the evolution of polyploidy in sturgeons,
111 potential for hybridization to confound the resolution of phylogenetic relationships, a lack of
112 morphological synapomorphies for a newly defined *Acipenser*, and concerns about negative
113 conservation consequences stemming from the change of genera for many species of
114 *Acipenseridae*.

115 The SSG also cites Kottelat and Freyhof (2025), who suggested that some nomenclatural
116 acts in Brownstein and Near (2025) were erroneous, but this misrepresents the nature of that
117 contribution. Kottelat and Freyhof (2025) accepted the phylogenetic taxonomy of *Acipenseridae*
118 and agree that all genera recognized by Brownstein and Near (2025) are monophyletic; their sole
119 objection is the opinion that *Sterletus* Rafinesque, 1820 is a senior synonym of *Huso* Lovetzky,
120 1834. Brownstein and Near (2026) argue that *Sterletus* qualifies as a *nomen oblitum* and *Huso* as
121 a *nomen protectum* under the ICZN, resolving the dispute. The SSG's invocation of Kottelat and
122 Freyhof (2025) as evidence against the revised taxonomy conflates a limited nomenclatural
123 disagreement among scientists who share the same phylogenetic conclusions with a substantive
124 rejection of those conclusions.

125 These criticisms, taken together, raise questions that extend beyond the specific case of
126 sturgeons. Here, we use the case of sturgeons to illuminate this view. The argument that policy
127 impacts on conservation necessitate the retention of taxonomies that do not reflect phylogeny is
128 pragmatically motivated but inverts the causal relationship between systematic biology and
129 conservation policy. Allowing policy frameworks to constrain the taxonomy that informs them
130 does not protect conservation outcomes but undermines them by preserving classifications that
131 misrepresent the evolutionary diversity those frameworks are designed to protect. To illustrate
132 why we hold this view, we first show that the proposed retention of *Acipenser* paraphyly settled
133 on by the SSG fails to meet their own stated goal of having taxonomy that reflects natural history
134 and organismal biology. The nature of the SSG's argument exemplifies a pattern in which
135 concerns about the practical costs of taxonomic change are used to resist classifications that more
136 accurately reflect phylogeny.

137

138 **The Claim of Weak Statistical Support**

139 The SSG places particular emphasis on bootstrap support values as a basis for rejecting
140 the phylogenies presented in Brownstein and Near (2025), stating that the revision reflects "weak
141 statistical support for many of the clades presented." Bootstrap support values are continuous
142 measures of support provided by the data for a particular clade, not threshold criteria for the
143 existence of clades. The convention of treating bootstrap values above 70% as indicative of
144 meaningful support is long established in the phylogenetic literature (Alfaro et al. 2003; Hillis
145 and Bull 1993). Importantly, all the monophyletic groups that Brownstein and Near (2025) use in
146 our proposed taxonomy are supported by bootstrap values exceeding 93% in at least one
147 analysis; the reciprocal monophyly of three genera (*Acipenser* sensu stricto, *Sinosturio*,
148 *Scaphirhynchus*) is supported by bootstrap values of 100% across all analyses. Species
149 traditionally placed in *Pseudoscaphirhynchus* also resolve in a clade with 100% bootstrap
150 support across all analyses, although *Pseudoscaphirhynchus* is nested deeply within *Huso* in the
151 phylogeny inferred using mtDNA. The only genus of sturgeons in the taxonomy of Brownstein
152 and Near (2025) supported by bootstrap values of less than 100% in some analyses is *Huso*.
153 However, the consistent resolution of the lineage identified as *Huso* in different analyses
154 supports the monophyly of this clade (Brownstein and Near 2025; Brownstein and Near 2026).

155 Congruence across independent datasets with different evolutionary histories and
156 different sources of systematic error is itself powerful evidence for a phylogenetic hypothesis. A
157 cytochrome *b* gene tree, a phylogeny inferred from DNA sequences of 30 nuclear genes, a
158 phylogeny inferred from concatenated nuclear and mitochondrial genes, and a phylogeny
159 inferred from 62 discretely coded morphological characters all infer the traditional delimitation

160 of *Acipenser* and *Huso* as not monophyletic (Figure 1). Most critically, much of the diversity of
161 sturgeons remains classified in paraphyletic groups regardless of which data type is analyzed.

162

163 **The Missing Data Objection**

164 The SSG raises concerns about missing data in the molecular matrix, noting that the "entire
165 systematic [sic] is based upon a data set that contains substantial missing data." This objection
166 conflates a general methodological concern with a specific claim about the Brownstein and Near
167 (2025) analysis.

168 The 30 single-copy nuclear orthologs were drawn from a curated dataset in which paralogs had
169 been explicitly filtered out prior to publication (Luo et al. 2019). The concern about missing data
170 is legitimate as a general methodological consideration, but modern phylogenetic methods,
171 including the maximum likelihood and Bayesian approaches used by Brownstein and Near
172 (2025), handle missing data by estimating likelihoods conditional on observed data. Extensive
173 simulation studies have demonstrated that phylogenies with substantial missing data can be
174 highly accurate when the available data are informative (Roure et al. 2013; Wiens 2003; Wiens
175 and Morrill 2011). Missing data are only a problem if they are distributed in a way that
176 systematically misleads the analysis. The SSG does not demonstrate that the pattern of missing
177 data in the Brownstein and Near (2025) matrix produces biased results.

178

179 **The Introgression and Hybridization Argument**

180 The SSG argues that introgression of mitochondrial and nuclear loci among sturgeon species can
181 confound molecular phylogenetic results, which undermines their confidence in the phylogenies
182 presented in Brownstein and Near (2025). Sturgeons are known to hybridize both in nature and

183 in aquaculture (Birstein et al. 1997; Havelka and Arai 2018; Ludwig et al. 2009; Schrey et al.
184 2011; Schrey et al. 2007; Tranah et al. 2004; Vasilyeva et al. 2019), and hybridization has been
185 documented among species across multiple genera in aquacultural settings (Zhang et al. 2013).
186 Hybridization is a potential complication in sturgeon systematics, as introgression confounds
187 phylogenetic inference across vertebrates (Luo et al. 2026; Rancilhac et al. 2024; Santos et al.
188 2025). However, the species complexes most extensively documented as involved in
189 hybridization and introgression are all placed in the same genera in the new phylogenetic
190 taxonomy (Brownstein and Near 2025). Hybridization between species is not likely to lead to
191 error in reconstructing phylogenetic relationships among more inclusive clades. The
192 introgression problem would be most damaging to the revised taxonomy if hybridizing species
193 were in different genera; the opposite is true. The intergeneric hybridization documented in the
194 literature occurs between lineages whose separation at the generic level is precisely what the
195 revised taxonomy reflects.

196 Brownstein and Near (2025) directly address one case where introgression appears to
197 have influenced the topology: the incongruence between the mitochondrial and nuclear
198 phylogenies for *Pseudoscaphirhynchus*. The mtDNA gene tree infers that species
199 of *Pseudoscaphirhynchus* are nested within *Huso* as the sister clade to *H. stellatus*, whereas
200 nuclear gene phylogenies and concatenated analyses resolve *Pseudoscaphirhynchus* as sister to
201 all *Huso*. Brownstein and Near (2025) interpret this incongruence as likely reflecting ancient
202 mitochondrial introgression from a *Huso* lineage into the ancestor of *Pseudoscaphirhynchus* and
203 treat the nuclear gene inferred phylogeny as the primary signal for genus-level delimitation.
204 Dillman et al. (2007) also highlighted the conflict between morphological and molecular datasets
205 for *Scaphirhynchinae*, concluding that "at least one of these two data sets does not reflect the true

206 history of these species." This acknowledgment, which comes from the paper the SSG cites as a
207 primary methodological authority, establishes that incongruence between data types is a known
208 and expected feature of sturgeon phylogenetics.

209

210 **The Polyploidy Objection**

211 The SSG states that the Brownstein and Near (2025) revision "does not align with the phylogeny,
212 especially the polyploidy events in the family," implying that the history of whole-genome
213 duplication in *Acipenseridae* is inconsistent with the inferred phylogenies. Chromosome counts
214 alone are insufficient to reconstruct the history of polyploidization in a group as complex as
215 sturgeons, where ploidy levels vary across and within species and where the correspondence
216 between chromosome number and ploidy history is not straightforward (Ludwig et al. 2001;
217 Vasil'ev 1999; Vasil'ev 2009). The claim that polyploidy conflicts with the Brownstein and Near
218 (2025) topology cannot be evaluated without specifying what topology the history of
219 polyploidization predicts and why, something the SSG statement does not provide. The SSG
220 acknowledges that whole genome sequencing data were presented at ISS 10 and that these data
221 provide higher taxonomic resolution but does not state whether these unpublished data conflict
222 with the published phylogenetic taxonomy. Those data have not been published or incorporated
223 into a competing phylogenetic analysis. Importantly, a published phylogenomic analysis of
224 sturgeons that includes only eight species resolves the traditional delimitation of *Acipenser* as
225 paraphyletic and relationships among the sampled species are similar to those in the phylogeny
226 we used to construct the rank-free taxonomy (Brownstein and Near 2025; Liu et al. 2022).
227 Critically, the mitochondrial genome is not subject to nuclear whole-genome duplication events,
228 so the concern about polyploidy does not apply to the mitochondrial component of the

229 Brownstein and Near (2025) analysis. The polyploidy objection as currently stated by the SSG
230 does not constitute a specific falsification of the phylogeny of sturgeons.

231

232 **The Morphological Synapomorphies Objection**

233 The SSG states that the Brownstein and Near (2025) taxonomy "is not supported by
234 synapomorphies in morphological characters" and that "those morphological features named are
235 not defined and therefore not readily applicable." Brownstein and Near (2025) explicitly
236 acknowledge the absence of known morphological synapomorphies for *Acipenser* sensu stricto.
237 The absence of recognized morphological synapomorphies for a clade does not mean the clade
238 does not exist, but only that morphological synapomorphies have not yet been identified or
239 described. The monophyly of many major lineages of ray-finned fishes was validated only after
240 the application of molecular data and these clades lack substantive morphological
241 synapomorphies (Betancur-R et al. 2014; Dornburg and Near 2021; Miya et al. 2003; Near et al.
242 2025; Near and Thacker 2024), so the SSG criterion would require rejecting the results of
243 phylogenomic analyses conducted across the globe over several decades. That morphological
244 synapomorphies are unknown for some clades is expected rather than exceptional, and perhaps
245 especially so in sturgeons, which are among the most morphologically conservative of all
246 vertebrates (Bemis et al. 1997; Hilton and Grande 2023; Hilton et al. 2011; Vasil'eva 1999;
247 Vasil'eva 2009).

248 More fundamentally, this objection applies with equal force to the classification the SSG
249 proposes to maintain. The traditionally recognized, broadly defined *Acipenser*, paraphyletic in
250 every published analysis, has no morphological synapomorphies either, because it is not a natural
251 group. Demanding morphological synapomorphies as a precondition for accepting a molecularly

252 supported clade sets a standard that the existing classification does not meet and that the SSG
253 does not apply to itself. Dillman et al. (2007) themselves noted a fundamental conflict between
254 morphological and molecular datasets in *Scaphirhynchinae*, a traditional taxonomic group that
255 includes species of *Pseudoscaphirhynchus* and *Scaphirhynchus*. Phylogenetic analysis of
256 morphological characters supports monophyly of *Scaphirhynchinae*, but molecular data
257 consistently reject it. This conflict illustrates that morphological characters in sturgeons can
258 mislead as readily as they can clarify.

259

260 **The Internal Contradiction of the Proposed Alternative**

261 Specifically, the SSG proposes dissolving both *Huso* and *Sinosturio* and transferring all their
262 species into a broadly defined *Acipenser*, yielding three genera: *Acipenser*, *Scaphirhynchus*, and
263 *Pseudoscaphirhynchus*. Paradoxically, this proposed classification maintains a paraphyletic
264 *Acipenser*. Dillman et al. (2007), the paper the SSG treats as its primary methodological
265 authority, presented molecular phylogenies where *Acipenser* is resolved as paraphyletic,
266 dispersed among three separate clades. Thus, the argument presented by the SSG is not that the
267 results presented in Brownstein and Near (2025) are wrong, but rather that nomenclatural
268 stability should be prioritized over phylogenetic accuracy. This outcome is an almost inevitable
269 consequence of Linnaean ranked classification: when a ranked taxon is demonstrated to be
270 paraphyletic, the Linnaean framework provides no principled mechanism for resolving the
271 conflict between nomenclatural priority and phylogenetic accuracy. The result is exactly what
272 the SSG proposes: expanding a paraphyletic group to absorb a formerly recognized taxon,
273 producing a familiar name with an even less accurate phylogenetic content. The SSG's position

274 acknowledges that *Acipenser sensu lato* is paraphyletic while insisting that the paraphyly be
275 preserved in the name of stability.

276

277 **The Dillman et al. (2007) Citation in Context**

278 The SSG explicitly invokes Dillman et al. (2007) as a justification for resisting taxonomic
279 change, quoting the statement that "the taxonomy of sturgeon species should not be altered on
280 the basis of any single data set...[and] we do not feel that the data sets assembled to date provide
281 sufficient resolving power to alter any currently recognized genera." The SSG asserts that this
282 conclusion "remains true today."

283 The SSG's invocation of Dillman et al. (2007) requires careful examination. That paper
284 was written before the 30-gene nuclear dataset used by Brownstein and Near (2025) existed. The
285 caution it expressed was explicitly directed at analyses based on limited mitochondrial data
286 subject to the dramatically reduced substitution rates that Dillman et al. (2007) themselves
287 documented. The concern that any single dataset might be insufficient is addressed directly by
288 the multi-dataset approach of Brownstein and Near (2025), which integrates congruent signal
289 across the mitochondrial gene cytochrome *b*, 30 single-copy nuclear orthologs, morphological
290 characters, and combined analyses.

291

292 **The Conservation Argument**

293 The SSG argues that the revised taxonomy could negatively impact the conservation of sturgeons
294 by disrupting species names embedded in CITES listings, IUCN Red List assessments, the EU
295 Habitats Directive, regional instruments such as HELCOM and the Bern Convention, and
296 domestic legislation such as the U.S. Endangered Species Act. We acknowledge that regulatory

297 frameworks are built around names, and that changes to those names create administrative
298 burdens that are not trivial when the organisms in question are critically endangered and subject
299 to active enforcement actions at international borders. However, the conservation argument for
300 maintaining an inaccurate classification rests on a premise that does not survive scrutiny: that an
301 inaccurate taxonomy is a neutral baseline whose costs are zero, while a revised taxonomy carries
302 costs that must be weighed against its benefits (Morrison et al. 2009). An inaccurate taxonomy is
303 not a neutral baseline (Thomson et al. 2018), but an active source of conservation risk (Clavero
304 et al. 2024).

305 We contend that paraphyletic genera misrepresent the scope and structure of evolutionary
306 diversity in ways that mislead conservation decision-making. When species from deeply
307 divergent lineages are subsumed under a single familiar genus name, conservation managers,
308 policymakers, and the public may perceive them as variations on a theme rather than as
309 representatives of independently evolved lineages with distinct evolutionary histories, ecologies,
310 and conservation needs. The five lineages formalized as genera by Brownstein and Near (2025)
311 diverged from one another in the Cretaceous and early Paleogene. Treating them as a single
312 genus obscures the evolutionary history of sturgeon diversity, especially when a stated goal in
313 conservation biology is to preserve evolutionary history (Stein et al. 2018). This is the concern
314 that motivates the shift towards phylogenetic rank-free classification (Near et al. 2025; Near and
315 Thacker 2024): taxonomies that fail to represent natural groups are not merely misleading for
316 academic researchers but carry practical consequences for conservation planning and
317 management.

318 The delineation of Evolutionarily Significant Units (ESUs), an operational conservation
319 unit recognized under both U.S. and Canadian law and increasingly adopted in international

320 conservation frameworks, depend on phylogenies. Several definitions of ESUs include criteria
321 such as reproductive isolation, significant divergence of allele frequencies, restricted gene flow
322 from other lineages, and reciprocal monophyly in mtDNA gene trees (Fraser and Bernatchez
323 2001; Moritz 1994; Waples 1991). When taxonomy misrepresents phylogenetic relationships, it
324 can mislead ESU delineation in ways that have direct management consequences, causing
325 genuinely distinct evolutionary lineages to be managed as components of a single unit rather than
326 as independent conservation priorities. This is not a theoretical concern in sturgeons, where ESU
327 delineations have directly shaped conservation planning outcomes (Sulak et al. 2016).

328 The appropriate response to the practical challenges of taxonomic change in regulatory
329 contexts is not to freeze taxonomy in an inaccurate state but to develop better mechanisms for
330 updating legal and regulatory frameworks when taxonomy improves. Other groups of
331 conservation concern have navigated genus-level taxonomic revisions without catastrophic
332 consequences for their legal protection (Dulvy et al. 2021; Kitchener et al. 2017; Morrison et al.
333 2009). The argument that sturgeons are uniquely unable to survive a taxonomic revision is not
334 supported by evidence and sets a damaging precedent: that conservation regulatory frameworks
335 can veto scientific progress in systematics.

336

337 **The Procedural Problem**

338 The scientific objections raised by the SSG have been addressed in the preceding sections and do
339 not withstand scrutiny on their own terms. We raise the following procedural concern not as a
340 substitute for that scientific rebuttal, but because the mechanism by which the rejection was
341 produced has direct consequences for how its conclusions will be received and acted upon in
342 regulatory and legal contexts. The question of whether a revised taxonomy is adequately

343 supported by phylogenetic evidence is not one that a workshop vote is structured to resolve.
344 Conservation practitioners, regulatory officials, aquaculturists, and ecologists are exactly the
345 right people to evaluate the policy and management consequences of taxonomic change, as that
346 is a question on which their expertise is directly relevant and essential. But these are two distinct
347 questions, and a workshop vote conflates them in a way that does not serve either.

348 Unanimity in a vote on a scientific question is not the same as scientific consensus,
349 particularly when the question is a technical one about phylogenetic evidence. Scientific
350 consensus on a phylogenetic question is established through peer-reviewed publication,
351 replication, and the accumulation of congruent evidence across independent datasets. A
352 unanimous vote establishes that the SSG membership shares strong concerns about the
353 consequences of taxonomic change for conservation and regulatory frameworks. It does not
354 establish that the phylogenetic evidence presented in Brownstein and Near (2025) is flawed.

355 The SSG statement carries institutional weight that its scientific content does not support.
356 There is a real risk that its conclusions will be incorporated into regulatory and legal frameworks
357 before a thorough peer-reviewed response exists in the literature, which is precisely why we are
358 writing this paper. We encourage the broader systematics and conservation biology communities
359 to evaluate the competing taxonomic hypotheses on their scientific merits, in the peer-reviewed
360 literature, with the rigor these conservation stakes require.

361

362 **Conclusions**

363 The SSG rejection of Brownstein and Near (2025) exemplifies a problem that extends far beyond
364 sturgeons. As molecular and genomic data continue to reveal the extent to which Linnaean
365 ranked classifications misrepresent the tree of life, the transition toward explicitly phylogenetic

366 rank-free frameworks will increasingly intersect with conservation regulatory systems built
367 around familiar names. The response of those systems, and of the specialist communities that
368 advise them, will determine whether the improvements in biological classification that
369 phylogenetics makes possible are translated into better conservation outcomes or are resisted in
370 the name of stability.

371 The scientific objections raised by the SSG against Brownstein and Near (2025) do not
372 withstand scrutiny. The bootstrap support objection ignores the fact that the phylogenies
373 presented in Brownstein and Near (2025) are quite strongly supported and ignores the likely
374 effects of well-documented reduction in molecular evolutionary rates in *Acipenseriformes* that
375 systematically depresses support values regardless of signal quality. The missing data objection
376 invokes a general methodological concern without demonstrating that it applies specifically to
377 the Brownstein and Near (2025) dataset in a way that biases the results. The introgression
378 objection misidentifies the taxonomic level at which hybridization occurs and is addressed
379 transparently in the original paper. The polyploidy objection is asserted without an explicit
380 competing model and is not applicable to the mitochondrial component of the analysis. The
381 morphological synapomorphies objection demands a standard of evidence that the existing
382 classification does not meet and that is not applied symmetrically to the SSG's own proposed
383 alternative.

384 Most fundamentally, the SSG's proposed alternative, a broadly defined
385 paraphyletic *Acipenser*, fails on the very terms the SSG invokes. Every published analysis,
386 including Dillman et al. (2007), the paper the SSG treats as its primary methodological authority,
387 resolves *Acipenser* as paraphyletic. The SSG acknowledges this paraphyly and proposes to

388 preserve it anyway. This is not a scientifically defensible position; it is a preference for
389 familiarity over phylogenetic accuracy.

390 The conservation argument for maintaining the existing classification, while
391 pragmatically motivated, inverts the actual relationship between accurate taxonomy and effective
392 conservation. Paraphyletic classifications misrepresent evolutionary diversity and distort ESU
393 delineation in ways that have real consequences for the allocation of conservation resources. The
394 short-term administrative costs of taxonomic change are real but manageable; the long-term
395 conservation costs of maintaining an inaccurate classification compound silently and are borne
396 by the organisms themselves.

397 The Brownstein and Near (2025) revision of *Acipenseridae* is part of a coherent and
398 explicitly articulated research program aimed at constructing fish classifications that directly
399 reflect evolutionary relationships and are free of the structural limitations of Linnaean ranked
400 hierarchy. Near and Thacker (2024) demonstrated across the full breadth of ray-finned fish
401 diversity that Linnaean ranked taxa are not biologically comparable to one another in any
402 evolutionarily meaningful sense, that ranked classification produces redundant and
403 uninformative names at a striking rate, and that a *PhyloCode*-based rank-free framework
404 provides names with explicit, testable phylogenetic content that remain stable as phylogenetic
405 hypotheses are refined. Near et al. (2025) showed in *Labridae* that the practical consequences of
406 this problem are not abstract: polyphyletic and paraphyletic Linnaean genera actively confound
407 both biological research and conservation management, and that a blended approach, using
408 *PhyloCode* definitions that retain ICZN conventions at the genus and species level, provides a
409 pragmatic and scientifically rigorous path forward. Brownstein and Near (2025) brought this

410 same framework to *Acipenseridae* and for the first time produced a classification in which all
411 genera are monophyletic.

412 This research program is not iconoclastic; it follows directly from the phylogenetic
413 revolution in systematics applied to groups where the need for accurate taxonomy is most urgent.
414 The most endangered vertebrate lineage on Earth is exactly the kind of group for which getting
415 taxonomy right matters most. We urge the sturgeon conservation community to engage with the
416 revised taxonomy on its scientific merits, to recognize that phylogenetic accuracy and
417 conservation effectiveness are mutually dependent rather than competing values, and to
418 participate actively in the broader transition toward phylogenetic rank-free classification that the
419 evidence now overwhelmingly supports. A comprehensive genomic and morphological dataset
420 sufficient to definitively resolve sturgeon phylogeny is within reach, and building it, rather than
421 defending an inaccurate status quo, is the most productive investment the sturgeon community
422 can make in the decades ahead.

423

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634

635 **Figure Legends**

636 Figure 1. Three alternative taxonomies of sturgeons shown on a phylogeny of *Acipenseridae*
637 presented in Brownstein and Near (2025).

Phylogeny-based taxonomy

Traditional taxonomy

Sturgeon Specialist Group taxonomy

